

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF INNOVATIVENESS AND PROACTIVENESS ON FAMILY-OWNED RESTAURANTS PERFORMANCE IN ILORIN, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA

Dr. Ahmed ABDULKAZEEM¹, Prof. Adeyeye MODUPE-MERCY²&Dr. Fidelis FRED A IJANADA³

¹Department of Entrepreneurship and Business Studies.School of Innovative Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Nigeria.ahmedabdulkazeem@gmail.com 08036266912, 08121820200.

²Department of Entrepreneurship Studies, Faculty of Management Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria.memoad4real@yahoo.com 08034505871.

³Department of Entrepreneurship Studies, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, National Open University of Nigeria.fareeunique@gmail.com 07032242934.

Abstract

In today's dynamic business environment marked by market volatility, resource constraints, and increasing consumer demands, entrepreneurial orientation particularly innovativeness and proactiveness have become crucial, especially in developing economies. This study investigates how these dimensions influence the performance of family-owned restaurant businesses in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. A quantitative cross-sectional survey was conducted, targeting registered family restaurants. Due to the lack of an official registry, the population was treated as infinite, and a sample of 384 respondents was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. A multi-stage sampling technique, involving stratified and systematic random sampling, was adopted to ensure representativeness. Data were gathered using structured questionnaire and analysed with Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) via Smart PLS. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between innovativeness and business performance ($p < 0.05$), aligning with the Resource-Based View (RBV) that intangible assets like innovation offer competitive advantage. However, proactiveness showed no significant effect ($p = 0.944$) and even had a slight negative influence (beta = -0.018), suggesting misaligned anticipatory actions may not benefit resource-constrained family firms. The study concludes that while innovativeness enhances performance, proactiveness alone may be insufficient. Promoting customer-centric innovation and digital adoption could improve competitiveness. This research adds to entrepreneurial

orientation literature by highlighting contextual influences on family business success in emerging markets.

Keyword: Family Business, Performance, Innovativeness, Proactiveness.

JEL Classification: L26, L25, L83, O31, M13.

Introduction

In the contemporary business landscape marked by market volatility, limited resources, and increasing consumer expectations entrepreneurial orientation (EO) has emerged as a critical strategic framework, particularly within developing economies. EO integrates profit-making with social responsibility and environmental awareness, enabling firms to remain competitive while contributing to broader socio-economic goals (Bamgboye, 2024). Key components of EO are innovativeness that pursuit of new ideas, products, or processes; and proactiveness is the ability to anticipate and respond to future market trends (Beshr *et al.*, 2023). These traits are increasingly seen as essential for the survival and growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

Family businesses, often long-term in outlook and culturally embedded, play a significant role in both developed and developing economies (Zekeri *et al.*, 2024; Agbim, 2022). In Nigeria, SMEs contribute significantly to employment and socio-economic development (Odeyemi *et al.*, 2024). However, they face persistent challenges, such as informal management structures, limited resources, and weak access to innovation frameworks factors that hinder their ability to adapt to external shocks or seize emerging opportunities.

In Ilorin, Kwara State, family-run restaurant businesses contribute meaningfully to urban development through food services, job creation, and local economic stimulation. Yet, many of these enterprises fail to adopt sustainable practices or improve performance due to limited engagement in entrepreneurial activities. Despite global and regional evidence supporting the positive impact of innovativeness and proactiveness on business outcomes (Akinlo *et al.*, 2024; Nurudeen *et al.*, 2024), it remains unclear whether these EO dimensions are actively practiced within Ilorin's family-owned restaurants.

Existing studies in Nigerian cities such as Lagos, Oyo and Ilorin suggest that high levels of EO correlate with better financial outcomes, customer retention, and competitive positioning (Akinlo *et al.*, 2024; Nurudeen *et al.*, 2024). However, research has largely overlooked the unique characteristics of family-owned restaurants, whose conservative management styles may limit innovation and reduce responsiveness to consumer trends (Zekeri *et al.*, 2024). Many of these businesses also lag in technology adoption and proactive strategies, affecting their competitiveness and growth potential.

Although several studies have examined entrepreneurial orientation and firm

performance, limited empirical attention has been given to the specific roles of innovativeness and proactiveness in influencing the performance of family-owned restaurants, particularly within the context of Ilorin, Kwara State. This creates a knowledge gap regarding how these entrepreneurial capabilities contribute to business sustainability and competitiveness in family-based hospitality enterprises. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the impact of innovativeness and proactiveness on the performance of family-owned restaurants in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The findings are expected to provide empirical insights that will guide restaurant owners, policymakers, and entrepreneurship scholars in understanding how entrepreneurial orientation can enhance the performance and sustainability of family-owned businesses in the hospitality sector.

Grounded in the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory which posits that firm performance is driven by internal capabilities and unique, intangible resources such as knowledge and strategic orientation (Penrose, 1959; Barney, 1991). This study contributes to literature on family business strategy, and entrepreneurial practices in emerging markets. It also offers practical insights for policymakers, practitioners, and academics on supporting SME growth in dynamic and competitive environments.

Research Question

- i. To what extent does innovativeness influence the performance of family-owned restaurant businesses in Ilorin, Kwara State.
- ii. How far does proactiveness affect the performance of family-owned restaurant businesses in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Literature Review

Innovativeness refers to an organization's willingness and capacity to develop new ideas, experiment with products or services, and explore improved processes (Kwapisz *et al.*, 2022). It involves departing from routine practices, embracing creative thinking, and taking calculated risks to drive better performance. Within the framework of entrepreneurial orientation, innovativeness is seen as the continuous push toward progress, the creation of new technologies, and the identification of niche markets that meet emerging consumer needs. This trait is particularly critical for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as it fosters adaptability and competitiveness in dynamic market environments.

The strategic importance of innovativeness is often demonstrated through investment in research and development (R&D), process improvement, and the ability to introduce radical changes that reshape existing business models (Al-Suwaidi, Alshurideh *et al.*, 2021). While incremental innovations improve existing products and services, radical innovations involve launching entirely new solutions

that redefine market expectations. For SMEs, innovation provides a pathway to access new markets, integrate emerging technologies, and incorporate customer feedback to enhance product design and delivery.

Innovative SMEs often outperform their counterparts in customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and profitability. Ayoko (2021) found that innovation-oriented SMEs recorded stronger financial outcomes than those with limited innovation engagement. Similarly, Zaato *et al.* (2020) assert that innovativeness enhances a firm's ability to quickly respond to market risks and opportunities, making it more agile in a competitive landscape. Family-owned businesses in hospitality and food services have adopted innovations such as flexible menus, digital ordering, and personalized customer experiences to remain resilient in changing markets.

Despite these benefits, the adoption of innovativeness in Nigeria's family businesses remains slow due to cultural conservatism, limited financial resources, and weak innovation infrastructure. Many family-owned firms resist change due to traditional values, a lack of exposure to modern practices, or fear of uncertainty (Ooi *et al.*, 2025). However, even modest innovations such as incorporating digital tools for customer service or adapting products to local preferences can significantly enhance performance and customer engagement (Nurudeen *et al.*, 2024). The development of an innovation-oriented culture is therefore crucial. Firms that embed innovation into their strategy are more likely to achieve sustainable growth, increased competitiveness, and long-term market relevance. Innovativeness should not be viewed merely as an optional skill but as a vital strategic resource, especially for SMEs in resource-constrained and competitive environments.

In the context of this study innovativeness is examined as a key determinant of performance in family-owned restaurant businesses in Kwara State. These enterprises, though often bound by tradition, must embrace innovation to thrive in a fast-paced and evolving market. The ability to remain flexible, responsive, and creative will determine their survival and growth. Ultimately, promoting an innovation-driven mindset through research, experimentation, and strategic change can equip these businesses to better meet consumer expectations and sustain their relevance in the marketplace.

Proactiveness is a core entrepreneurial behaviour that reflects an organisation's ability to anticipate future trends, identify emerging opportunities, and act ahead of market changes. Rather than reacting to events, proactive firms shape their environments through foresight and strategic positioning (Anwar *et al.*, 2021). This includes launching new products early, entering untapped markets, or reallocating resources in anticipation of future customer needs. In fast-changing industries like the restaurant sector where consumer preferences, technology, and service formats evolve rapidly proactiveness is vital for competitiveness.

Proactive entrepreneurs are future-oriented and market-conscious, consistently scanning their environments to identify unmet needs and opportunities for growth (Okoli *et al.*, 2021). Instead of waiting for demand to appear, these firms forecast changes in consumer behaviour, regulation, or competition and take pre-emptive action. Through market sensing, adaptive planning, and strategic engagement, proactive firms maintain an edge over rivals.

Being proactive also enhances sustainable competitiveness. First-mover advantages allow firms to lead in product offerings, dominate niche markets, and build strong brand identities. Early adoption of trends such as healthier menu options, digital ordering systems, or community driven branding can significantly improve customer loyalty and market presence in the restaurant industry (Nurudeen *et al.*, 2024). This agility ensures that businesses remain relevant even amid economic or social disruptions.

For small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), especially family-owned businesses in Nigeria, proactiveness fosters a culture of innovation and strategic flexibility. These firms often operate with limited resources and face stiff competition from larger corporations. By anticipating customer needs, leveraging technology, and improving service quality, proactive SMEs can overcome structural limitations and achieve long-term performance (Akinlo *et al.*, 2024).

Importantly, proactiveness is not a passive response but a deliberate, forward-looking approach. It is closely tied to strategic competitiveness, organisational adaptability, and operational efficiency. In this study, proactiveness is viewed as a key performance driver in family-owned restaurant businesses in Ilorin, Kwara State a setting marked by intense competition, changing consumer preferences, and economic uncertainty. For these firms, heightened awareness and timely responses are essential for achieving and sustaining competitive advantage. Ultimately, proactiveness enables family businesses to transition from survival to growth-focused models. It equips them with the capacity to anticipate shifts, act with purpose, and remain resilient in dynamic environments ensuring their relevance and contribution to the local economy.

Family Business Performance has become a critical area of interest in entrepreneurship research due to the distinct nature of such enterprises. Unlike non-family firms focused primarily on profit, family businesses pursue both financial and non-financial goals such as preserving legacy, employing relatives, building social capital, and ensuring intergenerational wealth transfer (Yusuf & Abdulkzeem, 2024). As a result, their performance must be evaluated using multidimensional criteria, incorporating financial, operational, relational, and strategic indicators.

In emerging economies like Nigeria, family-owned businesses, particularly in the hospitality and food sectors, play a crucial economic role by generating employment and supporting local markets (Odeyemi *et al.*, 2024). However, their performance is

often hindered by informal management structures, limited access to finance, weak exposure to innovation, and inadequate training (Zekeri *et al.*, 2024). In the restaurant subsector, relevant performance indicators include customer retention, menu adaptability, service quality, profitability, and brand recognition. Yet, many of these businesses rely on intuition and informal feedback instead of structured performance measurement systems.

Performance in family firms is complex and context-dependent, influenced by various interacting factors (Perera & Samarakoon, 2021). Agbim *et al.* (2023) define it as the ability of a family-managed firm to achieve both business and familial goals, including generational ownership transfer. Success is measured not only by financial outcomes but also by the firm's capacity to use available resources to meet broader objectives. Ajani *et al.* (2024) further describe performance as the achievement of strategic goals, influenced by the lead entrepreneur's traits. Due to higher managerial discretion in family firms, non-financial metrics such as trust, customer loyalty, and employee commitment are often more valued than purely financial results (Pratono & Han, 2022). Therefore, understanding performance requires analyzing both internal dynamics and market responsiveness.

In summary, family business performance, especially in Ilorin's restaurant industry, must be seen through a holistic lens integrating innovation, customer satisfaction, adaptability, and growth. This study focuses on how entrepreneurial traits like innovativeness and proactiveness shape such performance, offering practical insights into sustainable success within family-run hospitality firms in emerging markets.

Theoretical Review

Resource-Based View Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV), initially proposed by Penrose (1959) and later advanced by Wernerfelt (1984) and Grant (1991), explains how firms achieve and sustain competitive advantage by effectively utilizing their internal resources. RBV emphasizes that strategic performance is driven by resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN). These resources, both tangible and intangible, shape a firm's ability to respond to external challenges while building internal strength.

The theory asserts that firms differ in resource endowments, and this variation contributes to differences in performance. As noted by Miller (2019), such resources go beyond physical assets like infrastructure and finance; they include intangible assets like brand reputation, innovation culture, and human capital such as expertise and entrepreneurial knowledge. In the context of family-owned restaurants in Kwara State, key RBV-aligned resources include intergenerational knowledge, localized innovation practices, and independent decision-making. These internal strengths

often unique to family-run businesses serve as strategic assets that support long-term success and market differentiation.

RBV also guides internal strategy development, helping firms leverage their competencies through tools like SWOT analysis. This enables business owners to align internal capabilities with market opportunities and to counter external threats effectively. When firms align strategic actions with core capabilities such as innovativeness and proactiveness they can respond faster to market demands, improve service quality, reduce costs, and drive sustainable growth. Therefore, RBV provides a suitable theoretical foundation for this study, offering insights into how internal entrepreneurial capabilities influence performance in family-owned restaurants. By treating innovativeness and proactiveness as internal strategic resources, this research explores how these capabilities contribute to improved performance in the competitive and dynamic hospitality sector.

In conclusion, the RBV framework is essential for understanding how family businesses can develop, sustain, and utilize their core strengths to survive, compete, and grow. It supports the analysis of internal factors particularly entrepreneurial traits as key drivers of performance in emerging market settings like Kwara State.

Review of Empirical Studies

Mburu (2019) examined entrepreneurial strategies among 201 small and medium-sized family-owned manufacturing firms in Nairobi, Kenya. Using a cross-sectional survey with questionnaires targeting CEOs, directors, and founders, the study employed both descriptive and inferential statistics via SPSS. Results revealed a strong positive relationship between creativity, risk-taking, initiative, and business success. Similarly, Zainal (2022) explored the influence of innovation orientation on Kuwaiti family businesses. Data from 114 firms were analysed using structural equation modelling (SEM). The study found that creativity, risk-taking, and future orientation significantly enhanced business performance, whereas openness to change and proactiveness showed no significant impact.

In Rwanda, Muhayimana *et al.* (2023) studied the effect of proactiveness on the survival of family-owned manufacturing firms in Kigali. Using data from 384 senior staff across 77 firms, and analysed with SPSS and multiple linear regression, the study confirmed that proactiveness is essential for long-term survival and continuity. Rachmawati & Suroso (2022) investigated the connection between entrepreneurial orientation and family business performance in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Using SEM and the Sobel test on data from 328 hotels, findings showed that the entrepreneurial mindset alone did not significantly influence performance. However, family involvement fully mediated the relationship, and gender moderated the influence of entrepreneurial desire on performance.

Ismail & AbdulKazeem (2024) assessed entrepreneurial tendencies and

performance of Nigerian family businesses, citing factors like low sales, high taxes, poor infrastructure, and limited resources as major constraints. Through content analysis, they found that risk-taking, creativity, and proactiveness were positively linked to performance. Their study recommended prioritizing radical innovation and continuous improvement to strengthen customer experience and competitive advantage. Across all studies, key entrepreneurial traits particularly creativity, proactiveness and in some cases, risk-taking, were consistently linked to improved performance in family businesses. The empirical evidence supports the notion that entrepreneurial orientation plays a critical role in sustaining and growing family-owned enterprises in various cultural and economic contexts.

Onobrakpeya, (2024) conducted a study on restaurants in Delta State, Nigeria, the study utilized a Cross-sectional survey of 384 restaurant customers and the findings that entrepreneurial strategies such as innovativeness and proactiveness significantly improve customer patronage and competitiveness of restaurants. Restaurants that introduce new menu offerings, creative service delivery, and proactive market responses perform better in a dynamic market environment. Entrepreneurial behaviour helps restaurants adapt to changing consumer preferences and market conditions. In another study by Bello *et al.* (2024) the study focused on hotels in Ilorin, Kwara State, survey research design was employed with 168 respondents from 3-star hotels. The findings reveals that entrepreneurial proactiveness significantly improves business sustainability in the hospitality sector. Proactive firms anticipate customer needs and adopt innovative service strategies.

The reviewed studies provide a rich set of data on the effects of various dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation (innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking) on the performance of family-owned businesses under different conditions. However, a review of Mburu (2019) reveals some of its limitations, especially on the methodological front. Although a cross-sectional survey and mixed-questionnaire format allow the researcher to gather a wide range of data, the fact that the study was conducted using descriptive and basic inferential statistics in SPSS and Excel may have limited causal or structural explanations regarding entrepreneurial strategies. Additionally, the use of less sophisticated analysis methods, such as ANOVA, weakens the results, particularly when compared to the SEM-based analysis in Zainal (2022), which uncovered more nuanced relationships between innovation orientation and company performance in Kuwait. Mburu's study is also more traditional in terms of EO constructs, focusing mainly on creativity, risk-taking, and initiative, and does not consider mediating or contextual factors such as family involvement, governance, or resource limitations factors that other studies focusing on EO, like Rachmawati & Suroso (2022) and Muhayimana *et al.* (2023), have addressed. Furthermore, the absence of longitudinal data limits the ability to trace changes over time or assess the sustainable impacts of business strategies on

company outcomes. While the study makes a valid contribution to understanding entrepreneurship in family firms in Kenya, it could be improved by adopting a multi-dimensional perspective on performance, considering owners' reflections, and accounting for environmental factors. Bello *et al.* (2024) and Onobrakpeya, (2024) shows a positive and significant improvement on restaurants and hotel businesses in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research design through a cross-sectional survey to examine the innovativeness and proactiveness on the performance of family-owned restaurants in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The cross-sectional method enabled the collection of data from a large number of respondents simultaneously. Due to the absence of a definitive list of such businesses, the study assumed an infinite population. To ensure the sample was statistically representative, the Taro Yamane (1967) formula was used, resulting in a sample size of 384 respondents. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed for enhanced accuracy and reduced selection bias. First, stratified sampling was used to categorise restaurants across key areas of Ilorin, Ilorin West, Ilorin East, and Ilorin South. Then, systematic random sampling was applied within each stratum, ensuring equal selection probability for respondents.

A structured questionnaire served as the primary data collection tool, focusing on two key entrepreneurial dimensions innovativeness and proactiveness as predictors of business performance. The instrument included both dependent and independent variables measured using established indicators. To analyse the relationships among the variables and test the research hypotheses, the study employed Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) using the SmartPLS software. This method was suitable due to the presence of latent constructs and multiple indicators in the research model. The approach provided robust insights into how internal entrepreneurial capabilities influence performance in family-owned restaurants.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Test of Hypotheses

Fig 1: Structural Equational Model

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

The model shows that Innovation significantly drives Family Business Performance, while Proactiveness has little to no effect on performance. The overall model fit appears strong, with high factor loadings and a substantial R-squared value.

Table 1: Summary of Cronbach Alpha

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.788	0.770	0.106	12.534	0.000
INNOVATION	0.711	0.703	0.058	12.299	0.000
PROACTIVENESS	0.737	0.728	0.059	12.566	0.000

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

Table 1 shows the reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha for three constructs: Family Business Performance, Innovativeness, and Proactiveness. All Alpha values exceed the 0.70 threshold, indicating strong internal consistency. Family Business Performance recorded the highest reliability at 0.788, followed by Proactiveness (0.737) and Innovativeness (0.711), confirming the reliability of the measurement items. The table also presents the sample mean, standard deviation (ranging from 0.058 to 0.106), t-statistics (all above 12), and p-values (0.000), confirming statistical significance at the 0.01 level. These results suggest low variability across samples and high reliability in measuring the constructs. The significance of the reliability coefficients strengthens the validity of the instruments used in assessing Family Business Performance, Innovativeness, and Proactiveness in this study, confirming that each construct was measured consistently and accurately across the

sample.

Table 2: Summary of Composite Reliability

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.858	0.831	0.032	26.902	0.000
INNOVATION	0.895	0.872	0.033	26.751	0.000
PROACTIVENESS	0.919	0.899	0.033	28.178	0.000

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

Table 2 presents model fit indicators showing strong values across all constructs. Original sample (O) values are high for Family Business Performance (0.858), Innovation (0.895), and Proactiveness (0.919), indicating strong relationships with their underlying factors. The sample means (M) closely align with the original values, reflecting data consistency. Standard deviations are minimal (0.032–0.033), suggesting tightly clustered data. T-statistics for all constructs range from 26.751 to 28.178, well above the accepted threshold of 2, with p-values of 0.000, confirming statistical significance at the 0.01 level. These results demonstrate that the constructs are not only statistically significant but also reliable and valid within the model. Overall, the indicators confirm strong model performance and meaningful relationships among Family Business Performance, Innovation, and Proactiveness.

Table 3: Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
INNOVATION -> FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.978	0.896	0.245	3.993	0.000
PROACTIVENESS -> FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	-0.018	0.065	0.253	0.071	0.944

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

The path coefficient analysis in Table 3 shows that innovation has a strong, positive, and statistically significant effect on Family Business Performance, with a coefficient of 0.978, t-statistic of 3.993, and p-value of 0.000, indicating significance at the 1% level. This implies that innovative practices greatly enhance performance in family businesses. Conversely, proactiveness shows a negligible and negative

relationship with performance (coefficient = -0.018), with a t-statistic of 0.071 and a p-value of 0.944, indicating no statistical significance. Therefore, while innovation is a key driver of performance, proactiveness does not significantly impact family business outcomes in this study.

Table 4: Summary of Total Effect

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
INNOVATION -> FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.978	0.896	0.245	3.993	0.000
PROACTIVENESS -> FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	-0.018	0.065	0.253	0.071	0.944

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

The total effect analysis shows that innovation significantly enhances Family Business Performance, with a strong path coefficient (0.978), high t-statistic (3.993), and p-value (0.000). In contrast, proactiveness has a negligible and insignificant effect, indicated by a near-zero path coefficient (-0.018), low t-statistic (0.071), and high p-value (0.944). This suggests that innovation is a key performance driver in family businesses, while proactiveness does not significantly influence outcomes in this context.

Table 5: Summary of R square

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.924	0.924	0.017	53.592	0.000

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

The model's R-squared value of 0.924 explains 92.4% of the variability in family business performance, indicating strong predictive power. This high value, supported by a t-statistic of 53.592 and a p-value of 0.000, confirms the model's statistical significance, relevance, robustness, and reliability in identifying key success factors like innovativeness and proactiveness.

Table 6: Summary of AVE

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.448	0.472	0.032	13.932	0.000
INNOVATION	0.624	0.628	0.022	28.050	0.000
PROACTIVENESS	0.655	0.660	0.018	36.487	0.000

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) shows moderate convergent validity for Family Business Performance (0.448), below the 0.50 threshold. However, Innovation (0.624) and Proactiveness (0.655) exceed this standard, indicating strong convergent validity. All constructs have high t-statistics (Innovation = 28.050, Proactiveness = 36.487) and p-values of 0.000, confirming the statistical significance of the AVE values and the reliability of the measurement model.

Table 7: F square

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
INNOVATION ->					
FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.820	0.899	0.539	1.521	0.128
PROACTIVENESS ->					
FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	0.000	0.075	0.120	0.002	0.998

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

Family Business Performance is the dependent variable, with innovation showing a large effect size ($F^2 = 0.820$), indicating strong influence. However, the impact is not statistically significant ($t = 1.521$, $p = 0.128$). Proactiveness has no effect, with an F^2 of 0.000, $t = 0.002$, and $p = 0.998$. Thus, innovation shows potential influence, while proactiveness contributes negligibly to performance.

Table 8: Summary of Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
INNOVATION < -> FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	1.302	1.273	1.187	1.349
PROACTIVENESS < -> FAMILY BUSINESS PERFORMANCE	1.241	1.221	1.118	1.318
PROACTIVENESS <-> INNOVATION	1.256	1.229	1.157	1.283

Source: Smart PLS4 (2025).

The Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratios assess discriminant validity and reveal potential issues in this model. The HTMT values for Innovation–Family Business Performance (1.302), Proactiveness–Family Business Performance (1.241), and Proactiveness–Innovation (1.256) all exceed the 0.85 threshold, with confidence intervals also above acceptable limits. These results suggest the constructs may not be sufficiently distinct, raising concerns about overlapping concepts and poor discriminant validity within the model.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Hypotheses Testing and Summary of Findings

- i. Innovativeness has a statistically significant positive effect ($p < 0.05$) on the performance of restaurant family businesses in Ilorin, Kwara State.
- ii. Proactiveness shows a statistically significant negative effect ($p > 0.05$) on the performance of restaurant family businesses in Ilorin, Kwara State.

Discussion of Result

Innovativeness and Performance (Significant Positive Effect)

The finding that innovativeness boosts family business performance in Ilorin supports RBV theory, which links unique resources to competitive advantage. Innovativeness, as an intangible asset, helps restaurants adapt, offer novel services, and stand out in Nigeria's dynamic market. This aligns with studies by Zainal (2022) and Ismail & AbdulKazeem (2024) on its importance for success.

Proactiveness and Performance (Negative Effect)

Contrary to RBV and past studies, proactiveness showed a weak negative link to performance ($\beta = -0.018$, $p = 0.944$). Unlike industries where early action offers advantages (Mburu, 2019), family restaurants may face resource limits, market saturation, or resistance to change (Muhayimana *et al.*, 2023), reducing the effectiveness of proactive strategies.

Conclusion: This study addressed how innovativeness and proactiveness influence sustainable entrepreneurship in restaurant family businesses. Findings show that innovativeness has a significant positive effect on performance, highlighting the importance of creativity, new service development, and technology adoption in boosting competitiveness and customer satisfaction. Conversely, proactiveness showed a negative, statistically insignificant effect, suggesting that anticipating change alone may not enhance performance without proper support or alignment. These results challenge existing literature and underscore the need for business owners to critically evaluate which entrepreneurial strategies drive practical value. Ultimately, innovativeness proved impactful, while proactiveness did not.

Recommendations:

- i. Restaurant family business owners and managers should enhance service delivery by developing user-friendly websites that facilitate seamless bookings, reservations, enquiries, and transactions, thereby improving customer experience and boosting business performance.
- ii. To gain a competitive edge, restaurant family businesses should proactively adopt digital technologies, enabling them to attract customers, stay ahead of market trends, and capitalise on emerging opportunities.

Reference

- Agbim, K. C., Tanko, I., & Paul, V. (2023). Characteristics and performance of family businesses in wuse market, abuja, fct nigeria. *FUDMA Journal of Accounting and Finance Research [FUJAFR]*, 1(1), 114-128.
- Agbim, K. (2022). Family involvement and performance of family-owned restaurants in abuja. *Baze University Journal of Entrepreneurship and Interdisciplinary Studies*, 1(1).
- Ajani, A. O., Olufayo, T. O., Abdulazeez, A. S., & Ademola, A. A. (2024). Entrepreneurial orientation changes practices and performance of selected registered smes in lagos state, nigeria. *Journal of the Management Sciences*, 61(6), 126-141.
- Akinlo, I., Sotimehin, K.O., Monday J.U., & Ladoye, M. O. (2024). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of small and medium enterprises in southwestern nigeria. (2024). *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*. 4627-4646
- Al Suwaidi, F., Alshurideh, M., Al Kurdi, B., & Salloum, S. A. (2021). The impact of

- innovation management in smes performance: A systematic review. *International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Systems and Informatics* (pp. 720-730). Springer, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58669-0_64.
- Ayoko, O. B. (2021). SMEs, innovation and human resource management. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 27(1), 1-5.
- Bamgboye, P. O. (2024). Entrepreneurship for sustainable development in nigeria. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 11(4), 250–256.
- Bello, A. N., Sogunro, E. O., & Adeniyi, M. (2024). Effect of Entrepreneurial Pro-activeness on Business Sustainability of some Selected Medium-sized Hotels in Ilorin Metropolis, Nigeria. *African Journal of Management and Business Research*.
- Beshr, B., Muhammad, S. K., Alaghbari, M. A., & Albo-Aainain, M. I. (2023). The mediating role of empowering workers in the relationship between the entrepreneurial orientation and operational performance of bahraini family businesses. *Resmilitaris*, 13(1), 1331-1341.
- Grant, R.M. (1991). The resource-based theory of competitive advantage: Implications for strategy formulation. *California Management Review*, 33(3), 114-135.
- Kwapisz, A., Schell, W. J., Aytes, K., & Bryant, S. (2022). Entrepreneurial action and intention: the role of entrepreneurial mindset, emotional intelligence, and grit. *Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy*, 5(3), 375-405.
- Muhayimana, V., Raphael, G., & Marcha, S. (2023). Pro-activeness and its effect on the survival of family-owned manufacturing companies in Kigali City, Rwanda. *International Journal of Research in Business & Social Science*, 12(5).
- Miller, D. (2019). The resource-based view of the firm. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Business and Management*. Vol. 1, Issue 1. DOI:10.1093/acrefore/9780190224851.013.123.
- Nurudeen, B. A., Olusoji, S. E., & Mubo, A. (2024). Effect of entrepreneurial pro-activeness on business sustainability of some selected medium-sized hotels in ilorin metropolis, nigeria. Vol. 15 No. 1 (2024). *African Journal of Management and Business Research*, (AJMBR).
- Odeyemi, O., Usman, F. O., Mhlongo, N. Z., Elufioye, O. A., & Ike, C. U. (2024). Sustainable entrepreneurship: A review of green business practices and environmental impact. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 21(2), 346–358.
- Okoli, I. E. N., Nwosu, K. C., & Okechukwu, M. E. (2021). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of selected smes in southeast, nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6(4), 108-115.
- Ooi, S. K., Yang, S., & Adeneye, Y. B. (2025). Sustainable development practices as a

- mediator: linking entrepreneurial orientation to smes business performance. *Asian Journal of Business Ethics*, 14, 177–201 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13520-025-00233-z>
- Onobrakpeya, S. A. (2024). Assessing the Effect of Entrepreneurial Marketing Strategies on Customers' Patronage of Restaurants in Delta State, Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 9(2), 150–164
- Penrose, E. (1959). The Theory of the Growth of the Firm (Vol. 27, Issue 2). *Oxford University Press*. DOI: 10.1093/qje/27.2.137
- Perera, L. S., & Samarakoon, S. M. A. K. (2021). Effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation on SMEs' Innovation Performance in Sri Lanka. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 55-63.
- Pratono, A. H., & Han, L. (2022). From Family Business Orientation to Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Prosocial Behavior in Family Business Performance. *Journal of Family Business Management*, 12(4), 923-937.
- Rachmawati, E., & Suhartanti, P. D. (2020). Effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Family Involvement on Family Business Performance: Case Study in Hotel Business in Yogyakarta. *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference of Business, Accounting and Economics, ICBAE 2020, Purwokerto, Indonesia*. European Alliance for Innovation. DOI 10.4108/eai.5-8-2020.2301127.
- Suroso** Anwar, M., Clauss, T. & Issah, W.B. (2021). Entrepreneurial orientation and new performance in emerging markets: The mediating role of opportunity recognition. *Journal of Management Science Review*. Vol 9(3) 57 – 68.
- Taro, Yamane. (1967). *Statistics. An introductory analysis*, 2nd Ed., new york: *Harper and Row*.
- Yusuf, I & Ahmed, A. (2024). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of family business: An empirical analysis. *Abuja Journal of Business and Management (AJBAM)*, Vol. 2, No. 2, 2024. 153-165.
- Zaato, S. G., Ismail, M., Uthamaputhran, S., & Owusu-Ansah, W. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurial orientation on smes performance in Ghana: The role of social capital and government support policies. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan (Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship)*, 22(2), 99-114.
- Zekeri, A., Kowo, S.A. and Tunde-Arigbade, O.T. (2024). Efficiency of small business: The case of nigeria. foreign trade: *Economics, Finance, Law*. 136, 5 (Oct. 2024), 110–126. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.31617/3.2024\(136\)08](https://doi.org/10.31617/3.2024(136)08).